

Compounds of Tungsten(VI) Oxytetrachloride with Nitroanilines, Aminobenzoic Acids, Aminophenols, Ketones, Amides, and Anilides

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Compounds of tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride with nitroanilines, aminobenzoic acids, aminophenols, ketones, amides, and anilides have been prepared, their properties studied, and structures discussed.

In earlier communications (this *Journal*, 1961, 88, 352) the action of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride on some amines and heterocyclic bases and that of WCl_6 with aminophenols, aminobenzoic acids, nitroanilines, amides, and anilides (this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 177) have been reported. The work has now been extended to study the preparation and properties of compounds of $WOCl_4$ with nitroanilines, aminobenzoic acids, aminophenols, ketones, amides, and anilides.

EXPERIMENTAL

Tungsten(VI) oxytetrachloride was prepared, as reported earlier, and extracted with CS_2 . The organic solvents were dehydrated and distilled. The other chemicals used were of B. D. H. or E. Merck's 'extra pure' quality.

In all the cases, except urea and benzanilide, a moderately strong solution of the base in benzene was slowly added to the solution of $WOCl_4$ in CS_2 with constant shaking till the precipitation was complete and the base was in slight excess. In the case of urea and benzanilide, the compound was prepared by adding an excess of $WOCl_4$ in CS_2 to a suspension of these in benzene and the mixture left for 48 hrs. in a dry atmosphere with frequent shaking. It was filtered, the precipitate washed with benzene till free of the base, and dried in a vacuum desiccator at the room temperature. Tungsten, chlorine, and nitrogen were estimated as described earlier.

General Properties.—The compounds are coloured, fairly stable in dry atmosphere, and insoluble in benzene and ether but sparingly soluble in CS_2 , EtOH, and acetone. These begin to hydrolyse when brought in contact with water and are decomposed by acids and alkalis.

DISCUSSION

An examination of the results (Table I) shows that four molecules of nitroanilines and aminobenzoic acids combine with one molecule of $WOCl_4$ and the compounds formed are similar to those obtained with aromatic amines (*loc. cit.*). The nitro and carboxyl groups do not co-ordinate in presence of a strong donor group like $-NH_2$.

TABLE I

Organic compound.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. <i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	$[\text{WO}(\text{NO}_2.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Dark brown	20.67	20.58	15.47	15.86	-	-
2. <i>m</i> - " "	Do	Light brown	20.43	20.58	15.78	15.86	-	-
3. <i>p</i> - " "	Do	Greyish brown	20.81	20.58	15.80	15.86	-	-
4. <i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	$[\text{WO}(\text{COOH}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Light pink	20.40	20.67	15.71	15.93	-	-
5. <i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	Do	Light blue	20.51	20.67	16.04	15.93	6.23	6.30
6. <i>o</i> -Aminophenol	$[\text{WO}(\text{OH}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Brown	32.69	32.86	25.10	25.33	4.84	5.00
7. <i>m</i> - " "	Do	Dirty green	33.13	32.86	25.26	25.33	-	-
8. <i>p</i> - " "	Do	Light green	32.90	32.86	25.48	25.33	-	-
9. Acetophenone	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5.\text{CO}.\text{CH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Blue	22.33	22.39	17.14	17.26	-	-
10. Benzophenone	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5.\text{CO}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Ash	17.16	17.20	13.16	13.25	-	-
11. Michler's ketone	$[\text{WO}\{(\text{CH}_3)_2.\text{N}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{CO}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Dirty yellow	13.33	13.00	9.93	10.02	-	-
12. Urea	$[\text{WO}\{(\text{NH}_2)_2\}_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Grey	31.87	31.61	24.09	24.37	18.79	19.25
13. Acetamide	$[\text{WO}(\text{CH}_3.\text{CONH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Dirty grey	32.03	31.84	24.52	24.54	-	-
14. Benzamide	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5.\text{CONH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Blue	22.14	22.27	17.10	17.17	-	-
15. Acetanilide	$[\text{WO}(\text{CH}_3.\text{CO}.\text{NH}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Light blue	20.78	20.85	16.17	16.08	6.32	6.25
16. <i>p</i> -Aminoacetanilide	$[\text{WO}(\text{CH}_3.\text{CO}.\text{NH}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Light blue	19.50	19.53	14.84	15.05	12.08	11.90
17. Benzanilide	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5.\text{CO}.\text{NH}.\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Greenish grey	16.48	16.29	12.30	12.55	-	-

In the case of aminophenols only two molecules of these combine with one molecule of $WOCl_4$, showing thereby the co-ordination of both $-NH_2$ and hydroxyl groups. The compounds are fairly stable, probably due to the formation of chelate compounds.

In the case of ketones, amides, and anilides four molecules of each combine with one molecule of $WOCl_4$ and the compounds are considerably stable. The carbonyl group present in these molecules being very reactive and also the affinity of tungsten towards oxygen being strong, it appears that chlorine is readily displaced to the outer ring and the compound obtained with urea may be represented as $[WO\{CO(NH_2)_2\}_4]Cl_4$. Similar results were obtained in the formation of compounds of WCl_6 with amides and anilides (*loc. cit.*).

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